

A Sensitive Method for the Determination of Nitrogen Dioxide in Air Using Solvent Extraction

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A new sensitive method for the determination of nitrogen dioxide in air is proposed. Alkaline solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline with sodium arsenite is used for absorbing nitrogen dioxide which later serves as a coupling agent also. *p*-Nitroaniline is used for diazotization and then solvent extraction is employed to enhance the sensitivity. Analytical parameters such as collection efficiency and stoichiometric factors have been studied and are found to be 94 to 96% and 0.72 to 0.75, respectively.

NITROGEN dioxide is considered as the most hazardous component among the oxides of nitrogen. It is emitted from various industries and automobile exhausts. It causes nausea, vomiting, vertigo with cyanosis, methemoglobinemia, pulmonary oedema, etc. and plays an important role in the creation of photochemical smog. The maximum allowable limit for industrial hygiene is 5 ppm.

The spectrophotometric methods used for the analysis of nitrogen dioxide are based on the conversion of nitrogen dioxide to nitrate or nitrite ion in a suitable absorbing medium for subsequent analysis. A number of Griess type reagents have been proposed for the determination of nitrite but only a few of them are utilized for the determination of the atmospheric nitrogen dioxide¹⁻³. Some of the important drawbacks of these methods are instability of the coupling reagent, low collection efficiency and stoichiometric factor. Several modifications have been suggested to increase the collection efficiency and stoichiometric factor. A new efficient absorbing solution containing 8-hydroxyquinoline has been reported for the determination of nitrogen dioxide⁴. The present investigation deals with employing solvent extraction of the earlier reported method to increase the sensitivity. Present work reports an increase in sensitivity of the reaction to 1.5 fold and makes possible the determination of nitrogen dioxide at ppb levels. *Iso*-amyl alcohol is found to be the most suitable extractant in the present method.

Experimental

Apparatus : The spectral measurements were done with ECIL spectrophotometer, model GS 865 and Carl Zeiss spekol using 1 cm matched glass cells. pH measurements were made with ECIL digital pH meter, type pH 5651. Fritted midjet impingers (frit diameter 10 mm) of 35 ml capacity were used for air sampling. Calibrated rotameters were used for measuring the air flow rate.

Reagents : The absorbing solution was prepared by dissolving 200 mg 8-hydroxyquinoline and 100 mg sodium arsenite in 100 ml 0.1 *N* sodium hydroxide containing 2.5 ml ethanol.

Nitrogen dioxide was prepared by bubbling air through fresh nitrite buffer and acidic potassium permanganate as reported by Nash⁵ and later used by Nair and Gupta⁴.

Standard NO₂⁻ solution, 1 × 10⁻⁸ *p*-nitroaniline solution, 3 *M* sodium hydroxide solution and 10% w/v EDTA solution were prepared. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by the method of West. All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : 15 ml absorbing solution was taken in a midjet impinger and air was drawn through it at a rate of 0.75 l. min⁻¹. The solution was transferred to a separatory funnel and diluted to 100 ml. 1 ml *p*-nitroaniline reagent was added and acidity was adjusted to 0.5 *M* with hydrochloric acid. After 2 min an excess of sodium hydroxide was added. The purple coloured dye was extracted with 10 ml *iso*-amyl alcohol in two aliquots. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and the absorbance was measured at 570 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of NO₂ was computed from a calibration curve prepared from standard sodium nitrite solution after correcting with the stoichiometric factor. The interference due to heavy metals and SO₂ were masked by adding EDTA and H₂O₂ solutions, respectively prior to the addition of sodium hydroxide.

Results and Discussion

In alkaline absorbing medium nitrous acid exists as nitrite ion which is stable. The following reaction takes place.

Every substance competing with NO₂ for the OH radical will increase the NO₂ : NO₂⁻ stoichiometric factor to higher than 0.5. The compounds

containing reactive hydrogen atom such as phenols, aromatic amines, etc., have been investigated for this purpose and found to be capable of getting more than 90% efficiency compared to 33.5% collection efficiency of sodium hydroxide alone⁵. In the present method 8-hydroxyquinoline acts as coupling reagent for colour production while it also helps in increasing the NO₂ : NO₃⁻ stoichiometric factor and the collection efficiency. Sodium arsenite not only improves the collection efficiency of the absorbing solution but also enhances the stoichiometric factor which is due to reduction of any NO₃⁻ formed to NO₂⁻ ion. This has also been found by other⁶.

Present method is highly sensitive and efficient. Sensitivity of the method ($\epsilon = 3.88 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ computed from NO₂⁻ concentration) increases to 1.5 times after extraction ($\epsilon = 5.85 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ computed from NO₂⁻ concentration)⁷. The purple coloured dye extracted in *iso*-amyl alcohol has maximum absorption at 570 nm. The dye shows no change in absorbance upto 24 hr and after 36 hr the change in absorbance is within $\pm 2\%$. The absorbance remains constant from 15 to 40°.

The collection efficiency of the absorbing solution was found to be 94-96% in the first impinger at the recommended flow rate and NO₂ : NO₃⁻ stoichiometric factor ranged from 0.72 to 0.75 as reported earlier⁴.

Since the method is developed for the determination of nitrogen dioxide in air, a study on the effects of foreign species commonly found with nitrogen dioxide is studied. Interference studies were made by adding solutions of known amount of foreign ions in the absorbing solution before sampling and then analysing by the proposed procedure. It has already been reported that interference from heavy metals can be masked with EDTA and interference due to sulfur dioxide can be removed by using H₂O₂ (Table 1). Other air pollutants like CO, CO₂, NH₃, phenols, aniline and formaldehyde, benzene, xylene and toluene have no effect on the colour development. Effect of ozone could not be studied due to non-availability.

The method has been applied to polluted air samples and is more sensitive than the commonly used method.

Application of the method in analysing scooter exhaust and work room air :

The present method was applied for the analysis of nitrogen dioxide in scooter exhaust and work room air. Sample air from work room and scooter exhaust were divided into two parts and each part was analysed separately. First part was analysed by the present method while the second by the method of Nash⁸. The results obtained (shown in Table 2) were in full agreement with each other

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Concentration of nitrite = 4 μg^* ; Corresponding concentration of nitrogen dioxide absorbed = 5.4 μg

Diverse Ion	Masking agent	Tolerance limit ^{**} ppm
Be ²⁺	—	100
Ca ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺	1 ml 10% EDTA	100
Bi ³⁺ , Sb ³⁺	1 ml solution potassium tartrate	100
Fe ²⁺	—	50
Se ⁴⁺ , F ⁻ , Br ⁻ , Cr ⁶⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , W ⁶⁺	—	100
SO ₂ ⁻	—	800
PO ₄ ³⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻	—	200
SO ₃ ²⁻	H ₂ O ₂	50
I ⁻	—	25
Phenol, aniline, formaldehyde, benzene, toluene, xylene	—	25

* 100 ml deionised water was used for extraction.
** Concentration that causes $\leq 2\%$ error.

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF AIR CONTAINING NITROGEN DIOXIDE

Source of sample	Volume of sample (l.)	Nitrogen dioxide found (μg)	
		Present method	Nash's method
Scooter exhaust	5.0	2.8	2.9
	10.0	4.6	4.8
	15.0	7.0	7.0
	20.0	10.2	10.0
	25.0	12.5	12.2
Work room air*	40.0	4.0	4.2
	80.0	7.8	7.5
	120.0	10.0	10.2

* Biological samples were kept for wet digestion.

indicating the validity of the method for analysis of nitrogen dioxide in air.

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